

Paper 27

Business Strategy Of Top Indian Company : IBM

Ayshath Napiha M , Ayshath Safwana

College of Computer & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India E-mail:

ayshathnapiham36@gmail.com

Safwanasafful@gmail.com

Abstract

International business machines corporation (IBM) is an American multinational information technology company head quartered in Armonk, Newyork, United state with operation in over 170 countries. The company began in 1911 as computing-tabulating recording company (CTR) and was renamed “IBM” in 1924. IBM globally has a little over 4,00,000 employees. THINK was a one word slogan developed by IBM founder Thomas J Watson. IBM serves various industries like computer hardware, connectivity, IT services. IBM india pvt lmtd is the indian subdiary of IBM. it has facilities in Ahmedabad, Delhi and more cities and having head office in Bangaluru. For the fiscal year 2017 IBM reported Earnings of US \$5.7 billion with an annual revenue of US \$7.91 billion. The net worth of IBM is \$170.90 billion. IBM is the worlds ninth largest information technology company by revenue. IBM manufactures and markets computer hardware, middleware and software, and providing consulting services in areas ranging from mainframe computer to non-technology. IBM invented Hard Drive, floppy disk, IBM solid Logic Technology. The competitors of IBM are HP, Accenture, Xerox, Computer Science Corporation.

In this paper we have identified and discussed various business strategy of IBM by studying its operational strategy, service strategy, technology adoption strategy, HR strategy, finance strategy, marketing strategy, and new product development strategies. The paper also includes the company’s innovation on sustainability through green strategy and corporate social responsibility strategy. Finally, based on SWOC analysis, some suggestions are given to speed up the sustainable growth.

Keywords: IBM, Case study, Welcome to possible, Business strategy of IT Company

1. INTRODUCTION

International Business Machine corporation (IBM) is an American multinational information technology company headquarterd in Armonk, Newyork, with operations in over 170 countries. IBM produces and sells computer hardware, middleware and software, and provides hosting and consulting services in areas ranging from mainframe computers to nanotechnology. IBM is also a major research organization holding the record for most U.S patents guarented by a business for 26

consecutive years. Inventions by IBM include the automated teller machine (ATM), the floppy disk, the hard disk drive, the magnetic stripe card, the relational data base, the SQL programming language, the UPC barcode, and dynamic random-access memory (DRAM). The IBM was founded on June 16, 1911, by Charles Ranlett Flint. It has a net income of worth 79.591 billion U.S. dollars and total equity of 19.91 billion dollars. Around 366,600 employees are working under IBM Corporation.

2. OBJECTIVES

- To understand the type of products and services provided by the company.
- To analyze the overall growth of the company.
- To find the different initiatives that will help in environmental sustainability.
- To understand the HR training strategies and corporate social responsibilities of the company.
- To find the competitors of IBM.

3. ABOUT IBM TECHNOLOGIES

IBM began as the computing-Tabulating Recording company (CTR) and was renamed “International Business Machines” in 1924. IBM, frequently referred to as “Big Blue”, got its start in hardware and prospered in that business for decades, becoming the top supplier of mainframe computers. Five decades since the launch of the IBM System/360, the company continues to sell mainframe – class computers. IBM positions its z Systems product line as enterprise infrastructure for its customers' cognitive business. IBM targets a range of solutions for its z Series products including analytics, blockchain, cloud and DevOps. IBM's varied software line includes offerings such as IBM Cognos Analytics, IBM SPSS, IBM Maximo Asset management and DB2.

4. SMART PRODUCTS AND SERVICES Server hardware

Five decades since the launch of the IBM System/360, the company continues to sell mainframe-class computers. IBM positions its z Systems product line as enterprise infrastructure for its customers' cognitive business. IBM targets a range of solutions for its z Series products including analytics, blockchain, cloud and DevOps.

Meanwhile, the company aims its Power Systems enterprise servers toward big data and analytics applications. Power Systems run IBM's AIX and IBM i OSes as well as Linux. In another nod to open source, IBM introduced its LinuxONE system as a hardware platform.

Storage

On the hardware side, IBM offers products including its FlashSystem all-flash arrays, Storwize systems and other hybrid arrays, Fibre Channel storage-area network hardware, storage media, and tape products. The company is making a push into software-defined storage with its Spectrum Storage suite and Cleversafe object storage technology.

Software

IBM's varied software line includes analytics offerings such as IBM Cognos Analytics, IBM SPSS, IBM Maximo Asset Management and DB2. Many of IBM's products in this field came through acquisition: The company purchased Maximo in 2006, Cognos in 2008 and SPSS in 2009. IBM also

provides IT infrastructure software including its WebSphere Application Server and MQ messaging middleware. The company's software lineup in the mobile and social space includes the IBM Verse business email offering and the IBM Notes collaboration product. In addition, IBM's security software includes MaaS360 for mobile device security and IBM QRadar Security Intelligence Platform, a security information and event management product.

IBM customers may acquire software licenses through Passport Advantage, the company's licensing program for larger enterprises, or Passport Advantage Express, a program designed for medium-sized businesses. Fix Central, meanwhile, is an element of IBM support that provides fixes and updates for IBM customers' software and operating systems. Fix Central provides hardware support, as well.

Services

IBM's service units include Global Business Services, which houses Big Blue's management consulting operations, and Global Technology Services, which provides mobility, networking, business continuity and outsourcing, among other services. Like other large IT services providers, in recent years, IBM has moved to purchase companies offering cloud consulting and implementation services. In 2016, for example, IBM purchased Bluewolf, a Salesforce channel partner and cloud consultant. Bluewolf was folded into IBM's Interactive Experience practice, which is part of Global Business Services. In 2015, IBM acquired Meteorix LLC, a Workday services partner.

Cloud

IBM's SmartCloud software and services offering got off the ground in 2011. That move was followed in 2013 by IBM's acquisition of SoftLayer Technologies Inc., an infrastructure as a service provider. Following that deal, SmartCloud and SoftLayer were grouped together in a cloud services division. Since then, however, IBM has coalesced its cloud services offerings around its Bluemix platform as a service offering. As of fall 2016, Bluemix had incorporated SoftLayer cloud products and services into a broader portfolio of infrastructure, platform and application services. IBM's more integrated cloud offering competes against such rivals as Amazon Web Services, Google and Microsoft.

Cognitive offerings

The IBM Watson supercomputer, which pulls together artificial intelligence and analytical software, is the company's flagship cognitive computing offering. A number of technologies and discrete products have spun out of IBM's cognitive computing system and its related research. Customers, for example, can use Watson APIs to embed cognitive computing components into their applications. IBM also offers products with built-in cognitive capabilities. Those offerings include the IBM Watson Internet of Things Platform and IBM Watson Analytics for Social Media. IBM has looked to leverage its cloud technology as it rolls out Watson-related products. Watson APIs, for example, are available via Bluemix.

Research and development

Thomas J. Watson Jr., who succeeded his father as IBM CEO in 1956, put the company on a research and development track. Big Blue's research center, launched in 1961, encompasses research labs in Yorktown Heights, N.Y. and Cambridge, Mass., as well as an industry solution lab

in Hawthorne, N.Y. Notable developments out of IBM's research center include the invention of dynamic random access memory and the Fortran language. More recent research endeavors include blockchain, quantum computing and cognitive technology.

IBM also invests heavily in semiconductor research as it investigates chips to support cloud computing and big data systems. But while Big Blue conducts research on silicon, the company exited the microelectronics manufacturing business in 2015, selling that operation to GLOBALFOUNDRIES.

5. ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH GREEN STRATEGY

The five elements of nature form the very basis of creation. Earth, Fire, Water, Wind and Atmosphere sustain all forms of life on this planet, working in tandem to give us life as we know it. As organizations and individuals, we can make conscious efforts to respect their influence and make responsible investments and actions in ensuring our sustenance. What can businesses do to grow without compromising the ecosystem we live in?

The 'Atmosphere' envelopes all, supportive and enduring in its presence, like the overall organization. We are a Responsible Business that values ethics, strong governance and run the day to day operations based on our core philosophy- Employees First, Customer Second (EFCS) [38].

'Fire', warm and bright, kindling ambitions and illuminating the environment, represents the 'inner fire' that burns brightly in every one of our employees, representing their desire to create and lead change. We strive to continuously redefine the Workplace that facilitates transformational actions led by employees and embraced by the management.

'Earth', diverse and nurturing, sharing with us glorious bounty that we must pass on to future generations, reminds us that we have a duty to renew our Ecosystem.

'Wind', inspiring and unfettered, characterizes change. It cannot be seen but its influence can be felt. Purity of the spirit and heart, clarity of thought within the mind and focused intent are all characteristics of this element. This element represents the commitment our employees have to Repay Society as gentle winds of change

'Water', flowing and persevering, signifies how we innovate along this transformational journey and break barriers. IBM has established a framework to tackle the environmental impacts of the Company operations like carbon emissions; water use, waste generated, and materials procured and consumed, impact on biodiversity, travel, and transport in the context of supporting and enhancing in the company activities. This strategy has been developed in consultation with the employees working on the company and other staff and represents a framework for action to be taken

6. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

- Capacity building for nongovernmental organizations
- Solving community problems
- Making cities smarter
- Using technology to inspire young learners worldwide
- Using technology for teacher professional development
- Developing Entrepreneur Ecosystems

- Citizen engagement through corporate volunteering program
- Responding to Natural Disasters

7.SWOT ANALYSIS

Strengths

1. First mover in cloud computing solutions for enterprises
2. Brand reputation
3. Diversified business
4. Strong competency in acquisitions
5. Integration of products and services

Weaknesses

1. Expensive service and software solutions
2. Focus mainly on large enterprises

Opportunities

1. Expand services and software divisions
2. Increasing demand of cloud based services
3. Expensive service and software solutions
4. Focus mainly on large enterprises

Threats

1. Increasing competition in the cloud computing market
2. Slowing growth of world economy

8. COMPETITORS

► Hewlett Packard is an IT company that manufactures and sells Personal computers (PCs), software, IT services and solutions to large enterprises, medium-sized companies and [individual](#) consumers. The company was founded in 1939 in the USA with headquarters in Palo Alto, California. It employs over 5,000 persons and by mid- year 2017 its sales were close to \$100 billion and had a market capitalization of around \$14 billion.

► As of the end of the year 2017 statistics, [Xerox](#) had a market capitalization of close to \$8 billion, a sales value of around \$16 billion and approximately 40,000 employees. [Accenture](#) was founded in the year 1989 to provide computer services and solutions to various industries i.e. the telecommunications industry, health and Public Service, the [banking](#) and insurance industry, the energy industry et cetera.

► Ranked position 204 in [Forbes](#), Accenture made sales of around \$40 billion in the year 2017. Its market Cap. For the same year was approximately \$80 billion and employed around 500,000 people around the globe. The company was founded in the year 1906 in the USA and has its headquarters in Norwalk, Connecticut. In the year 2017, Xerox, one of the top brands in the world was ranked as the leading world employers

9. CONCLUSION

International Business Machines (IBM) specialize in Computer hardware, Computer software, Consulting and IT Services. The general business activity IBM are categorized as being part of the Information Technology Services Industry. For SWOT Analysis, strengths and weaknesses determine IBM's capabilities and challenges based on the organization's characteristics. The opportunities and threats in IBM's business reflect the situation of the information technology industry. IBM company adopts 3 grand strategies which is growth, stability and defensive strategy. For growth strategy, IBM has made expansion and joint

venture. For stability strategy, IBM enterprise applications to delight the customer. For defensive strategy, they launch an 'open' cloud computing strategy appears to doubt about the transparency of the plan. Competitive rivalry is the highest-intensity force in IBM's industry environment. This must take the highest priority in strategic formulation of IB

REFERENCES

- [1] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Industry Analysis – The First Step in Business Management Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 1-13. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810347>.
- [2] Aithal, P. S., (2017). Company Analysis – The Beginning Step for Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(1), 1-18. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.573769>.
- [3] Jithin Raj, K. & Krishna Prasad, K. (2018). A Critical Study on Business Strategies of 3i Infotech Ltd. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 13-21. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1247319>.
- [4] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An Effective Method of Developing Business Case Studies based on Company Analysis, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 16-27. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.400579>.
- [5] Aithal Architha & Aithal, P. S. (2018). How and Why Wharton Business School became World Topper – A Case Study on Organizational Quest for Excellence of First US Business School. *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAIEEM)*, 7(1), 15-42. ISSN 2319 – 4847, DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1164718>.
- [6] Keerthan R. & Aithal, P. S. (2018). A 'Desi' Multinational – A Case Study of Hindustan Unilever Limited. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 1-12. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1147365>.
- [7] Aithal P. S., Anil Kumar, Madhushree, & Revathi R. (2018). Investigation of Business Strategies in Higher Education Service Model of Selected Private Universities in India. *International Journal of Computational Research and Development (IJCRD)*, 3(1), 77-100. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1209910>.
- [8] Madhushree, Revathi R. Anil Kumar, & Aithal, P. S. (May 2018). Business Strategy of Top Indian IT Company: MindTree. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 22-36. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1249871>.
- [9] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Factor Analysis based on ABCD Framework on Recently Announced New Research Indices, *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences*

(IJMTS), 1(1), 82-94. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.584105>.

[10] Aithal, P. S., (2017). ABCD Analysis as Research Methodology in Company Case Studies. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 40-54. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.891621>.

[11] Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P.M. (2016). Innovations in Private Universities : A Case of Srinivas University. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 250264. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161151>.

[12] Aithal, P. S. & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2017). Challenges and Opportunities for Research& Publications in Higher Education. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 2(1), 42-49. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.400619>.

[13] About Us | IBM. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.ibm.com/about-us>

[14] IBM (2019, Jan 30). Retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ibm> [29] Autonomics And Orchestration | ibm. (n.d.).